

Two-Slit Interference Separating Particles in Time as Well as Space?

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Two-slit interference is usually described in terms of space alone, i.e. $\text{intensity} = |\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}_1) + \exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}_2)|^2$. The usual approximation is to take \mathbf{r}_1 and \mathbf{r}_2 as being parallel and differing in length by $d \sin(\theta)$, where d is the slit separation and θ , an angle made with the y -axis if the 2-slits lie along the x . This leads to an intensity pattern of peaks of different heights and widths suggesting a probability resolution scheme in space.

Now, two-slit interference implies one does not know through which slit a particle passes. If one idealizes the situation and argues that one knows the time at which an incoming particle reaches the 2-slit apparatus and the time this single particle reaches the detector (and its x position), then assuming that uncertainty due to the wavelength is small, one may calculate $\text{distance} = \text{velocity} * (\text{detector time} - \text{arrival at slits time})$. This ray may emanate from the detector x point to determine through which slit the particle passed if one assumes zero interaction time. Interaction time, however, cannot be zero, but we suggest that for one to be unsure through which slit the particle passes, there must be a minimum interaction time of $d \sin(\theta) = v \Delta t$, where $v = p/m$. A particle arriving at a specific x point on the screen, associated with a given θ , is also linked with a specific minimal interaction delay time which changes with θ . This is in addition to the extra time it takes for the particle to traverse longer rays from the detector to larger θ values. Thus there is not only an inherent uncertainty in x , but also built-in Δt delays associated with each x on the screen, we argue.

Two-Slit Apparatus

A two-slit apparatus is complicated because not only is there interference, but also diffraction from each slit and presumably some wavelength-frequency issues at the detector. As a result, we simplify the scheme here to consider only interference from the 2-slits and almost 0 errors in measuring arrival time at the 2-slit apparatus and at the detector as well as almost 0 error in measuring the x value at the detector. Even with these idealizations, we find that there must be an interaction time linked to θ .

It is well-known that one may calculate the intensity at the screen by:

Intensity proportional to $|\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}_1) + \exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}_2)|^2$ ((1))

A traditional simplification is to consider \mathbf{r}_1 and \mathbf{r}_2 parallel to each other such that one ray is long than the other by:

$d \sin(\theta)$ ((2)) Here d is the distance from the center of one slit to the center of the other.

((2)) is then set equal to $n * \text{wavelength}$ for peaks and $(n + .5) * \text{wavelength}$ for troughs. ((3))

As a result, ((1)) shows x-space at the screen broken into distinct Δx resolution regions with different probabilities. Here the 2-slit apparatus lies along the x-axis and θ is the angle made with the y-axis.

Given that $|p|=mv$ (nonrelativistic case of a particle with rest mass m) and that the larger θ , the longer the ray from the center of the two slits to the screen, a particle arrives at a large θ later than it arrives at a smaller one.

What we wish to investigate here is whether there is a θ dependent extra Δt due to an interaction time which ensures that one cannot determine through which slit the particle passes. In other words, ((1)) is a purely spatial equation, but we suggest that it is associated with a θ dependent interaction time which separates points along the x axis at the screen in time (beyond regular travel time).

Interaction Time Considerations in the 2-Slit Apparatus

Here we idealize the situation and assume that one knows at which time a particle arrives at a 2-slit apparatus. We also assume that one knows a sharp x at which it arrives at a detector and a sharp time. These are idealizations and one would expect some frequency-wavelength corrections. The point we make is that even with these idealizations, one is required to have a θ dependent interaction time in order to prevent the detector from knowing through which slit the particle passed.

If one considers ((1)) with r_1 and r_2 parallel (as an approximation which almost applies if the screen is very far away from the 2-slit apparatus), then:

Peaks occur for $d \sin(\theta) = n \cdot \text{wavelength}$ where $n=1,2,3\dots$ ((4))

If one knows the x point at the detector, then:

Distance traveled = $|p|/m$ (arrival time at detector - arrival time at slits) ((5))

Given x and the ray ((5)), one should be able to determine through which slit the particle passed if interaction time is zero. Interaction time, however, is not zero. The question then becomes: Is there a minimum interaction time which prevents one from guessing through which slit the particle passed? We suggest that a time linked with

$d \sin(\theta) = v \Delta t$ ((6)) where $v=|p|/m$

suffices. If one has such an interaction time, then it is possible that the particle passed through the longer path linked slit with 0 interaction time, or through the shorter path linked slit with a Δt interaction time. Thus, there seems to be a minimal interaction time due to θ even for a spatial analysis ((1)). This interaction time Δt is added to the time taken for the particle to move along a particular ray (say from the center of the 2-slit apparatus to the x point on the screen). As a result, there is not only a separating of regions of x due to interference (with each having its own width and probability), but each is associated with a minimum interaction time which separates the particle in time (extra time from the path traversal time).

Conclusion

A 2-slit interference pattern is usually considered to be a pattern in space with ((1)), a time-independent approach applied. Here, we argue that it seems there should be a minimal interaction time linked with θ . In other words, each peak is linked with a θ , width and probability, but also an interaction time (which is added to the path traversal time). This minimal interaction time is given by: $\Delta t = n \cdot \text{wavelength} / v$, where $|p| = mv$ for crests, we suggest. For troughs, it is: $\Delta t = (n + 0.5) \cdot \text{wavelength} / v$. We argue that one cannot determine at the detector through which slit the particle passed. This implies that one must have a minimal interaction time linked to the extra time spent traversing the longer path, say r_2 vector, given r_1 vector and r_2 vector. If the detector notices that the particle arrived at time t , then $t - t$ (arrival at slits) multiplied by v gives the length from x to slit 2 with 0 interaction time, but the particle may have passed through slit 1 with an interaction time of $d \sin(\theta) / v$, so one does not know through which slit it passed. If the interaction time is less than this (i.e. total time less than time linked with the traversal from slit 1 to the detector + a short interaction time), one would conclude that the particle must have passed through slit 1 and one cannot know through which slit it passed and still have an interference pattern.